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Density-Gradient Based Quantum Analysis of Nanowire Transistor

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ABSTRACT

The semiconductor devices scaling are changing very rapidly, which has triggered a non-conventional physical effect called quantum confinement. This dominant effect must need to be considered for submicron transistor modeling. The conventional drift-diffusion (DD) models are not suitable and accurate for analyzing the carrier distribution, energy levels and spatial confinement. This paper concentrates on employing Density-Gradient (DG) based quantum model for analyzing 3-D nanowire transistors made out of silicon and germanium. COMSOL Multiphysics 6.3 [1] has been used as simulation software. Extensive Simulation results reveal increased threshold voltage due to quantum effect, higher electron density at the center, and strong electrostatic control for the gate-all-around (GAA) structure.

Keywords:- Density-Gradient, quantum confinement, nanowire, electron concentration

INTRODUCTION

For a large structure of transistor, flow of carriers is explained by Poisson's equation and continuity equations. Due to the development of advanced semiconductor technology, size of the transistor is now shrinking below 5nm technology node. For this nanoscale device, conventional drift-diffusion physics model is no longer applicable. Because of the size of the channel approaches the electron de Broglie wavelength. In this condition carriers are not accumulated near the oxide layer. But those are transferred toward the center due to quantum repulsion force.

For nanoscale structure, device behavior such as: carrier concentration and energy levels are highly dependable on the quantum effects of the confined structures [2-5]. Density-Gradient (DG) quantum correction model is one of the best models to analyze the behavior of the nanowire transistor. This technique includes a quantum potential function, which represents the derivative of the carrier concentration. This resembles the quantum confinement effect, which is very much similar to the Schrödinger-Poisson model. And this model is comparatively easier for simulating 3-D device.

COMSOL the nanowire transistor with gate-all-around (GAA) model is a very efficient architecture for future technology because of its cylindrical structure, better control of carriers flow and reduced short-channel effects [6-7]. Multiphysics offer to simulate this nanowire device using the DG model by changing various characteristics parameters [8-9].

Through extensive simulation, this research evaluate the I-V characteristics, distribution of carriers in the channel, quantum potential and electrostatic potential for both silicon and germanium nanowire transistor. The obtained results are vital for clear understanding device

behavior due to the effects of quantum confinement. These also highlights the trade-offs between threshold voltage, bandgap, mobility, leakage currents that strongly influence the design of new and efficient transistor.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The simulation experiments are conducted by employing COMSOL Multiphysics Semiconductor Module with Density-Gradient (DG) quantum corrections module. Experimental setup consists of geometry construction, material assignment, physics setup, meshing, solver configuration, and result extraction.

Geometry

The geometry of the transistor is very important and influence the quantum confinement energy and also acts as the inputs to physics interface. The transistor layout is designed as a cylindrical nanowire channel with a diameter of 3.2 nm, which is surrounded by a 0.8 nm thick oxide layer. Source and drain of the transistor are set as 15 nm doped and extended on both sides of the channel. That makes the total transistor-length becomes 34 nm with a 4 nm gate area. The device is constructed as 3D solids, making sure to accurate representation of the oxide boundary, where quantum confinement takes place.

Materials

Several materials are available in the software for selection. However, silicon and germanium with dedicated model, which include bandgap, mobility, electron affinity, and permittivity, are considered for this selection. Oxide barrier height $\Phi_{\text{box}} = 3.15$ eV selected. The DG effective masses are defined with anisotropy ($m_x = 0.8 m_e$, $m_y = m_z = 0.12 m_e$), which resembles the real representation of quantum confinement in the radial direction.

Physics

The physics of the model is selected for solving several equations such as: electron and hole continuity equations Poisson equation, and drift–diffusion etc. Quantum corrections are also included, which compute the electron and hole quantum potentials based on density curvature. The boundary conditions are set as: gate voltage varies from 0 to 0.8 V, drain voltage = 0.05 V, doping concentration in the source/drain $N_d = 1 \times 10^{20} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, source voltage = 0 V.

Meshing

A suitable and refined mesh at the interface of semiconductor/oxide interface is needed because of the DG depend on second derivatives of carrier density. The selected mesh uses sub-nanometer resolution in these regions, with a coarser mesh elsewhere in order to increase computational efficiency.

Solver

The simulation study begins with an equilibrium step to find the initial carrier distribution. A stationary study then applies the applied biases. A continuation parameter is used for doping activation to stabilize the nonlinear system. Direct solver (PARDISO) in COMSOL is used to improve convergence.

Configuration

Data Extraction

Simulation results are extracted for further analysis, which include quantum potential distribution, current density vectors, 3D map of carrier concentration, electrostatic potential slices, and line profiles for $n(x)$ and $n(z)$. I_d – V_g curve are generated by gate voltage sweep.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Figure 1 presents the log-scale electron concentration and current density distribution within the nanowire MOSFET at the gate voltage $V_g = 0 \text{ V}$. The channel displays strong electron depletion at the center, demonstrating the presence of a built-in potential barrier without any gate bias. Instead of accumulating at the oxide interface, electrons are repelled toward the center due to quantum confinement.

This is a significant variation of distribution compared to classical inversion theory. The current density show that charge transport is largely restricted to the highly doped source and drain areas. These results demonstrate the significance of quantum-influenced carrier behavior in nanowire device. It has strong impact of accurate modeling techniques in order to predict conduction behavior.

Fig.1:-Log of electron concentration and current density distribution

Fig.2:-Hole Density & Electrostatic Potential Distribution

The figure 2(a) displays the hole concentration and 2(b) depicts electrostatic potential in the nanowire under equilibrium conditions. The plot demonstrates that holes are heavily suppressed in the n-type device, with very low concentration present in the channel and source/drain regions. An area of reduced carrier density is present toward the channel center. It indicates a natural depletion region is formed due to built-in electric field effects.

The electrostatic potential distribution depicts a gradual increase from source to drain. It shows the strong electrostatic control over the channel. The benefits of the gate-all-around structure are evident here, as the gate has the ability to control the entire perimeter of the nanowire. This ensures significant management of short-channel effects for advanced transistor technology nodes. Figure 3 shows the quantum potential profiles for electrons

and holes in the device. For electrons, the quantum potential becomes more positive near the center of the nanowire, effectively pushing them inward and away from the oxide interface. This causes the rise to a center-peaked electron distribution.

This is the result of strong confinement in narrow cylindrical channels. In contrast, the quantum potential experienced by holes shows an inverse pattern due to their different effective mass and transport behavior. It makes clear that quantum confinement has a major effect on charge localization on device characteristics such as threshold voltage and current flow.

These results also demonstrate that the quantum-corrected modeling approaches are more appropriate in this nanoscale regime. They provide realistic insight into the device geometry and material physics interact in order to influence the performance of such transistor.

Fig.3:-Quantum Potential Distribution: Electrons and Holes

Fig.4:- I_d - V_g (Silicon Left Germanium Right) Global: I_d (A)

The characteristics (I_d vs V_g) graph in figure 4, compares how silicon and germanium nanowire MOSFETs respond to increasing gate voltage. Germanium turns on earlier, demonstrating a lower threshold voltage because its carriers can populate conduction states with less applied energy. Once the device begins conducting, germanium also provides sufficiently higher drain current.

This advantage comes from its lighter effective mass and higher electron mobility, which allow charge to move more efficiently through the channel. The graph highlights that germanium is a strong candidate for high-performance

applications, which require comparatively fast switching-speed and higher drive current. On the other hand, silicon requires a higher gate voltage before the current rises rapidly.

This is the indication of stronger electron depletion and a deeper initial potential barrier against conduction. Though this phenomenon decreases the drain current as compared to germanium, it also improves off-state characteristics by lowering leakage current during non-conductive. These behaviors demonstrate that germanium excels in performance while silicon offers better electrostatic control.

Fig.5:-Concentration of Electron $n(x)$ for Silicon (left) and Germanium (right)

Figure 5 depicts the concentration of electron $n(x)$ of silicon and germanium at different points along the nanowire, from source to drain. At a lower gate voltage, both devices show significant changes in electron concentration near the midpoint of the channel. This behavior is due the built-in potential barrier that dominates the current flow during the off-state. Electron density for Ge is less deep than that of silicon, which causes the reduced energy gap and more efficient carrier transport. As the gate voltage increases, the electron concentration also increases throughout

the channel. This behavior demonstrates the confinement affects, where electrons can freely travel within the channel. In silicon, deeper depletion and lower carrier availability mean that more gate effort is required to form a strong conduction channel. It also demonstrates that channel formation is not uniform in deeply scaled transistor and the central region remains the most sensitive to electrostatic modulation. This is very critical in determining both threshold and on-state behavior.

Fig.6:-Electron concentration $n(z)$ for Silicon (Left) and Germanium (Right)

The electron concentration $n(z)$ of silicon and germanium on the radial dimension of the nanowire are shown in figure 6. This graph illustrates how electron density varies from the center toward the oxide interface. Both materials show clear evidence of quantum confinement, with electrons concentrated heavily toward the center of the nanowire rather than its surface. This is opposite to the traditional transistor theory, where carriers form a surface inversion layer. At the nanoscale of this device, the quantum repulsion from the oxide boundary forces electrons inward, and reshaping the distribution significantly.

Silicon demonstrates a strong peak resulting in a more significant reduction in carrier density as electrons move toward the boundary line. This leads to a higher threshold voltage and strong electrostatic control but it limits the current significantly. Germanium maintains a higher concentration profile across the wire radius, resulting in better conduction and mobility.

The radial analysis therefore shows that confinement effects differently for various materials and play a major role in performance. This figure also emphasizes the quantum-aware modeling is essential radial confinement directly determines how effectively a gate-all-around structure can influence the entire volume of its channel.

CONCLUSION

This manuscript presents a detailed 3D simulation and analysis of a nanowire transistor using the Density-Gradient (DG) quantum correction model implemented by using COMSOL Multiphysics. The results emphasize the importance of quantum modeling in the nanoscale, where traditional drift-diffusion models are unable to predict physical behaviors such as: carrier density, threshold voltage, and

radial charge distribution. The simulation results reveal the confinement effects, which are predicted by Schrödinger-Poisson by employing DG quantum potentials in to the COMSOL's semiconductor physics with increased efficiency.

Experimental results demonstrate that carrier distribution in the nanowire is strongly influenced by quantum confinement, forcing carriers away from the oxide layer and toward the center of the channel. This confinement altered subthreshold behavior, increased threshold voltage, and changed carrier mobility. Due to the lighter effective mass and higher mobility, Ge generates higher on-state current and turn-on earlier at the cost of potentially higher leakage current. However, Si provides lower leakage current and suitable thermal behavior with reduced drive current. This is because of its wider band gap and stronger confinement.

The gate all around structure proves highly effective in controlling the electrostatic potential, contributing to excellent subthreshold behavior in both silicon and germanium nanowire. Numerical stability and accurate representation of confinement are ensured by the application of DG physics. The I-V characteristics, carrier density maps, and quantum potential distributions are well suited with the expected characteristics mentioned in published articles [10-13]. So the proposed simulation approach is validated and confirmed.

This work demonstrates the necessity of quantum modeling for designing transistors in future technology nodes in advanced semiconductor applications. The DG method provides a powerful middle state between computationally expensive quantum mechanical models and the classical models.

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